

**EFFECT OF EMPLOYER BRANDING DIMENSIONS CSR,
PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND TRAINING AND
DEVELOPMENT ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION**

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Abstract

The purpose of the current research study is to investigate the employee retention and their crucial issues for firms in several sectors, including the healthcare industry. In the healthcare industry, the presence of trained and competent personnel is vital for delivering high-quality patient care. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to retain bright staff. High rates of employee turnover in the healthcare industry may lead to a loss of specialized knowledge, interruptions in the consistent delivery of service, and reduced levels of patient satisfaction. The population of the study was health care employees of "Hospital" in KP Peshawar. The participants were employees of nursing department only. In this case, the sample size is computed to be $n = 361$. Researcher used a probability sampling strategy. The sample selection was conducted using a random sampling method, relying on reputable sources from the Human Resources department and the hospital administrative unit. The organized questionnaire was included topics such as corporate social responsibility, perceived organizational support, and training and development. Data was analyzed with the use of SPSS v.20.0 and Frequency, Percent, t-test, and Regression analysis test were applied for result. The findings of the study showed that application and interest values positively

effect on Employer Branding Dimension on Employee Retention. The research contributes to the existing literature on employer branding for betterment their carrier development, and provides guidance to owners and managers when building successful employer brands within their organizations. The findings of this study aim to provide valuable insights for healthcare organizations striving to enhance their retention strategies through effective employer branding.

Keywords: Employer Branding, Employee Retention, Health Sector, Project Management

Introduction

The turnover rate in the healthcare business, specifically for nurse vacancies, has significantly increased from 13 percent to 37 percent compared to prior years (Roche, 2015). The selected hospital had a significant rate of employee resignations, leading to a scarcity of personnel, a decline in the performance of the healthcare system, and a terrible reputation. Khan, A. A., & Khan, M. (2010). The World Health Organization predicts that there will be a shortfall of 15 million health professionals worldwide by 2030. In some affluent nations, a 40% rise in nurse turnover is attributed to low remuneration and wage packages, as well as less incentives. Increasing demands without new hiring, especially in nations undergoing population growth that heightens the vulnerability to infectious diseases, the ongoing pandemics have caused significant devastation to the global economy, resulting in widespread job losses and negatively impacting daily life. As to the United States Department of Health & Human Services, healthcare institutions are projected to have a shortage of around 4.2 million nursing personnel, representing a 29% rise from the current unemployment rate of 8%. Haq, F. I. U., Alam, A., Mulk, S. S. U., & Rafiq, F. (2020)

The registered nursing workforce is experiencing a decrease due to the phenomenon of “ageing out,” which is impacting the health industry. However, there is a simultaneous increase in patient volume as baby boomers

are demanding a higher number of healthcare services Alam, A., Malik, O. M., Ahmed, M., & Gaadar, K. (2015) The health service has issued a request for nurses to return and assist with non-emergency surgical operations. Additionally, a new facility is being opened to accommodate the increased number of ICU nurses, who are experiencing fatigue and seeking reduced risk or professional advancement (Hidayat-ur-Rehman, et.al. (2021)).

Ensuring employee retention is a crucial issue for firms in several sectors, including the healthcare industry. In the healthcare industry, the presence of trained and competent personnel is vital for delivering high-quality patient care. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to retain bright staff. High rates of employee turnover in the healthcare industry may lead to a loss of specialized knowledge, interruptions in the consistent delivery of service, and reduced levels of patient satisfaction. Consequently, healthcare businesses are progressively acknowledging the need of adopting efficient techniques to maintain their staff.(Banerjee, 2018).

An increasingly popular method that has garnered much attention in recent years is employer branding. Employer branding is the strategic effort to shape and promote an organization's reputation as a highly desirable employer, with the goal of recruiting and keeping exceptional employees. The process includes establishing a favorable perception of the firm, emphasizing its distinctive value proposition, and effectively conveying the advantages of being employed by the organization. Healthcare businesses may improve their capacity to recruit and retain qualified healthcare workers by strategically presenting themselves as attractive employers (Hall-Ellis, S.D, 2014).Although employer branding has become more popular in many sectors, its precise implications and efficacy in the healthcare sector, especially in developing nations like Pakistan, have received less research attention. This study seeks to address the lack of research by examining how different aspects of company branding impact employee retention in the health industry, with a special focus on the Peshawar area.

Peshawar, situated in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa region of Pakistan, has a multitude of hospitals and healthcare institutions. The healthcare industry in Peshawar has difficulties with personnel turnover, which may be ascribed to issues such as restricted career advancement prospects, insufficient remuneration packages, and a dearth of conducive work conditions. Thus, comprehending the influence of employer branding aspects on employee retention within the particular setting of Peshawar's health sector might provide significant perspectives for healthcare businesses in formulating efficient ways to retain their workers.

This research will specifically examine four essential aspects of employer branding: corporate reputation, job qualities, organizational culture, and career growth prospects. The discovered characteristics are crucial elements that significantly impact employee perceptions and choices related to work satisfaction and retention. This research aims to analyze the correlation between these aspects and staff retention in order to provide evidence-based insights into the efficacy of employer branding efforts in the healthcare industry in Peshawar.

The results of this investigation are anticipated to enhance both theoretical and practical understanding. The project aims to gather empirical information on how employer branding factors affect employee retention in the healthcare industry. This will contribute to our knowledge of the link between these variables. The research results may practically aid healthcare businesses in Peshawar by facilitating the development and implementation of successful employer branding initiatives. This, in turn, can enhance employee retention and contribute to the establishment of a more stable and high-quality healthcare staff. The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of employer branding factors on staff retention within the healthcare industry in the Peshawar area. This research aims to gather significant information by examining the particular context of Peshawar's healthcare industry. The goal is to assist healthcare organizations in formulating strategies to recruit and

retain highly competent individuals, which will eventually lead to enhanced healthcare delivery and better patient outcomes.

Pakistan's population exceeds 229.5 million people, positioning it as the fifth most populated nation globally. The United Nations (UN) in 2022. There are a total of 919 hospitals, 560 Rural Health Centers, and 5334 Basic Health Units. The healthcare workforce consists of 33,427 nurses, 23,427 midwives, and 96,000 Lady Health Workers. It has all the essential physical resources to fulfill the needs of the people. The challenge is in effectively harnessing and integrating the skills and expertise of nurses and paramedics throughout the nation to get the intended outcomes. According to Anaiz Khwaja and Nasreen (2019), infectious/communicable illnesses make up around 40% of the overall disease burden.

According to Vindrola (2020) Factors such as fear of disease outbreaks, concern for family well-being, social isolation, containment measures, trust and confidence in healthcare facilities, awareness of risks and expectations, and stigma have all influenced the decision-making of healthcare professionals during pandemics. During an epidemic, hospital staff endures more shifts while facing high levels of stress, frequently with little resources, and willingly embrace the hazards associated with their profession. These factors may also render the official recommendations unattractive. Nurses are the most extensive category of healthcare workers that directly interact with patients. However, other healthcare professionals will also see a widespread shortage. Nursing shortages are prevalent in the USA, Canada, Scotland, Germany, England, and the Philippines (Aiken, 2019). Several sectors are grappling with a common challenge, namely a high incidence of employee turnover. The most significant and valuable asset of any organization is its staff members. Due to intense competition for skilled and capable personnel, employee retention is a crucial concern.

Significance of the Study

This study on the “Effect of Employer Branding Dimensions on Employee Retention: Evidence from the Health Sector in District Peshawar” is of critical importance for several reasons, both theoretically and academically. Theoretically, it contributes to the existing body of knowledge by exploring the intricate relationship between employer branding and employee retention within the specific context of the health sector. By examining the various dimensions of employer branding such as organizational culture, reputation, benefits, and career development opportunities this research provides a nuanced understanding of how these factors influence employees’ decisions to stay with their employers. This theoretical framework can be applied to other sectors and regions, thus broadening the scope of employer branding literature. The findings offer valuable insights for academics, practitioners, and policymakers interested in human resource management and organizational behavior. By highlighting the specific branding dimensions that are most effective in retaining employees, this research can guide healthcare organizations in developing targeted strategies to enhance their employer brand and reduce turnover rates. Ultimately, this study underscores the importance of strategic employer branding as a vital tool for maintaining a stable and committed workforce in the healthcare sector. It emphasizes the need for organizations to invest in their brand image not just for attracting talent, but also for retaining it, thereby ensuring long-term organizational success and improved patient care outcomes.

Literature Review

Branding of Employer

A brand is a set of characteristics that communicate ideals and exert influence on others (Swystun, 2007). A name, word, or design that has significant value for an organization and requires deliberate effort to develop and control is referred to as a valuable asset (Kotler et al., 2005). Branding may be defined as the systematic effort to establish and differentiate a brand. Organizations

are increasingly using branding as a strategic tool in the current economic environment. Branding is used to distinguish goods and organizations from one another, resulting in the creation of additional value (Sokro, 2012).

From an employee's standpoint, a corporation may also be considered a brand when it comes to its role as an employer. Ambler and Barrow (1996) describe the employer brand as the functional, economic, and psychological benefits of working for a company. The employer brand encompasses a broad variety of advantages and characteristics, including economic benefits like money incentives, as well as intrinsic rewards and the degree to which the employee's specific requirements are met (Edwards, 2010). The text elaborates on the strategic approach that covers all aspects of a firm's attempts to establish a favorable image and reputation among its present and future workers. It emphasizes the factors that attract and retain top talent to this organization (Lloyd, 2002).

Employer branding refers to the efforts made by an organization to enhance its reputation and the perception of individuals towards the organization (Lievens & Slaughter, 2016). Managing the perception of (possible) workers towards a certain organization is a complex and ongoing process that requires a long-term commitment (Mandhanya & Shah, 2010). Backhaus & Tikoo (2004) further state that employer branding is used to establish a recognizable and unique identity for a company. The company's distinct and exclusive values are integrated with human resources management to effectively communicate a distinctive image to workers (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004; Edwards, 2010). This graphic aims to depict an exclusive and distinctive employee experience that is only attainable by working at this particular firm (Sullivan, 2004). The purpose of employer branding is to communicate certain attributes and benefits that the business provides, demonstrating that working there is a distinctive and outstanding opportunity. The objective is to distinguish the employer from competitors and provide a unique experience to both existing and prospective workers

(Edwards, 2010).

Practices of Employer Branding

The proper strategy and execution are crucial for using employer branding as a competitive advantage. Evidence suggests that individuals have a more favorable view of a firm when it has a superior employer brand in comparison to its rivals (Jain & Bhatt, 2015). This is due to the fact that it establishes a favorable differentiation from other employers (Lievens & Slaughter, 2016). In order to do this, it is necessary to take into account many ways in the employer branding strategy, such as business culture, image and reputation (Maheshwari et al., 2017), perks, and career advancement (Dabirian et al., 2017). By including these variables within the plan, the employer brand may effectively convey its desired message (Edwards, 2010).

Organizational Culture

Hofstede defines culture as the common conceptual framework that distinguishes one group from another. The term originated from the examination of ethnic and behavioral distinctions among nations within the fields of sociology and anthropology (Wilson, 2001). Nevertheless, this concept was progressively incorporated into the corporate realm and emerged as a vital aspect for organizations (Baumgartner, 2009). Organizational culture, as defined by Schein (2004), encompasses the values, beliefs, attitudes, behaviors, and practices that influence individuals' actions and interactions within a group. These factors are evident in every aspect of an organization, including the physical workspace, the hierarchical arrangement, the scale of the firm, and the approaches to work (Gaddam, 2008). According to Lipton (1996), an organization's culture refers to the principles that support the organization's goal and vision, and has a substantial impact on the organization's identity and brand. The culture of a corporation is complex, diverse, and encompasses several components. In his work, Schein (2004) delineated three distinct layers that are ingrained inside an organizational culture (refer to Figure 1). They include of externally observable factors, such

as product or behavioral characteristics, as well as internally unobservable aspects, such as values and beliefs.

Compensation and Benefits

Another way of employer branding is the provision of perks by a firm, which may be more readily apparent than, for example, the organizational culture. The advantages include a broad spectrum and might possess functional, economic, or psychological significance (Edwards, 2010). The economic gains that workers get from employment are often associated with monetary pay. Primarily, the focus is on compensation, but other economic advantages may include healthcare, a financial contribution from the employer towards the employee's pension, or the sense of employment stability (Dabirian et al., 2017). Nevertheless, a satisfactory pay and monetary incentives alone are not enough to motivate workers to pursue a long-lasting and sustainable career. Employer branding management should also include other perks to attract and retain employees (McLean et al., 1996). These include items that might be categorized as indirect or non-monetary forms of compensation, as well as desirable attributes in the workplace (Klonoski, 2016). Many workers want a work-life balance, which allows them to effectively integrate their job and personal life, including family and leisure activities, without any problems. (Dabirian et al., 2017). Additional advantages may include provisions for time off or opportunities for professional growth and enhancement (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004). An exemplary employer brand strategy in relation to wages and benefits is shown by the inventor and automotive pioneer, Henry Ford. His staff has not only gotten higher salaries than employees in other organizations, but they have also been provided with long-term benefits, making it hard for them to consider resigning (Scott, 2016).

Career Growth and Support

Career growth refers to an individual's impression of the potential for advancement and development within an organization (Jans, 1989). For employers, this also entails the active cultivation of their workers and the

provision of appropriate assistance across the whole employee life cycle (Scott, 2016). To do this, a corporation must determine which individuals are eligible for promotion, and which need more training or qualifications to fill a vacant job inside the organization (Scott, 2016). According to Chang (1999), it is important for an organization to give priority to internal growth and provide sufficient training. Additionally, managers should be successful in providing workers with direction and help in their careers. Regarding employer branding, the aspect of career advancement and assistance is of utmost importance as it impacts the connection between the organization and its workers (Weng & McElroy, 2012). In addition, according to Dabirian et al. (2017), workers value the support of their employer and the opportunity to grow both professionally and inside the organization. This leads to increased staff commitment and reduced likelihood of turnover (Chang, 1999). In contrast, organizations that fail to provide possibilities for professional fulfilment and growth make work prospects offered by other employers more attractive (Weng & McElroy, 2012). Therefore, companies must ensure that highly skilled individuals have the opportunity to advance and grow within the organization in order to retain them (Ibrahim et al., 2018). This highlights the significance of career development as a crucial component of employer branding.

Advantages of Employer Branding

This chapter elucidates the advantages of employer branding when implemented well, after an explanation of several workplace branding tactics. According to Backhaus & Tikoo (2004), the individual performance of human resources operations, such as recruitment, workforce management, and employee growth, has a limited effect when conducted in isolation from one another. Managers may use employer branding to harmonies and integrate several activities into a unified plan, resulting in a more significant effect compared to carrying out each action individually (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004). Sullivan (2004) states that good employer branding leads to heightened firm

exposure and reputation, therefore persuading workers, managers from other organizations, and prospective candidates that it is among the top employers in the market. This hypothesis is supported by the research conducted by Chhabra & Sharma (2014), which revealed a significant correlation between seeing a brand as having a high image and the likelihood of applying. Employer branding is a strategy that emphasizes the good qualities of a firm and acts as a standard to differentiate it from other employers (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004).

Challenges of Employer Branding

Although a robust employer brand has the potential to recruit highly skilled individuals and enhance employee retention rates, it is important for companies to be aware of the hurdles involved in building and sustaining their employer brand. Creating a cohesive employer brand requires significant investment in terms of both finances and time. In certain cases, a dedicated committee or team with expertise in this area may be necessary (Gupta et al., 2014). Moreover, it is important to acknowledge that individuals vary in their wants and preferences. Consequently, people may choose to work for an organization for various reasons (Edwards, 2010)

Generational Management vs. Employer Branding

Regardless of the generation to which they belong, employees generally respond positively when their job is stimulating, they are fairly compensated, have opportunities for learning and career advancement, work with colleagues who share similar values, trust their immediate supervisor, and have competent leaders at the highest level (Deal et al., 2010). However, individuals' interpretation of an employer brand differs and is influenced by several demographic parameters, such as age (Jain & Bhatt, 2015). Generational differences are often noticed in three main areas: work ethic, adaptability to change, and perspectives on organizational hierarchy (Rood, 2011). Hence, managers should prioritize understanding their workers' viewpoints in order to successfully lead and guide them (Rood, 2011) via the use of different

employer branding tactics. In summary, this literature study has established a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, which will serve as a strong foundation for the subsequent chapters of this thesis. It has elucidated various strategies used in employer branding, underscored the significance of fostering employee loyalty, and shed light on the complexities associated with managing different generations in the workplace.

Employee Retention

Company performance depends on staff retention. Effective succession planning and employee satisfaction depend on an organization's ability to retain people. It significantly affects revenue and customer happiness, improving organizational results. Incentives to keep workers with a company are called employee retention. Happy employees prefer to remain with a company longer. If they care about their employees, companies can keep them. Companies that value their employees treat them properly. These organizations have accomplished much. The present government must improve HR department competitiveness to boost employee enthusiasm and retention. Keeping employees motivated and reducing turnover is what makes a company successful, not who they hire. HR is responsible for retaining workers. HR is vital to firm employee retention (Aruna & Anitha, 2015).

Talent Management

In today's globalised corporate world, self-generating companies gain greatly. Top management employs talent management to retain, attract, and hire top performers. This notion ensures long-term organization operation. Top management prioritizes talent because they believe they can innovate and boost output and efficiency (Bitner, 2008). Talent management is expanded to new areas to help the company find the finest individuals.

Conceptual Frame Work

Figure 1: Conceptual Frame work

Supported Theory

In the literature chapter of this study on the "Effect of Employer Branding Dimensions on Employee Retention: Evidence from the Health Sector in District Peshawar," the Social Exchange Theory (SET) serves as the foundational theoretical framework. SET posits that social behavior is the result of an exchange process where individuals seek to maximize benefits and minimize costs. This theory helps to explain the linkages between employer branding dimensions and employee retention.

According to SET, employees engage in a reciprocal relationship with their employers. When employers invest in strong branding dimensions—such as providing a positive organizational culture, fostering a good reputation, offering attractive benefits, and facilitating career development opportunities—employees perceive these as valuable rewards. In return, employees feel a sense of obligation to reciprocate by exhibiting loyalty and commitment to the organization, thereby enhancing retention rates.

The theory elucidates how each dimension of employer branding contributes to the overall perception of the employer-employee relationship. For instance, a positive organizational culture creates a supportive and engaging work environment, which increases job satisfaction and reduces

turnover intentions. Similarly, a strong organizational reputation enhances the pride employees feel in their association with the organization, making them less likely to leave. Attractive benefits and clear career development opportunities directly address employees' needs and aspirations, further solidifying their commitment to the employer.

Methodology

The quantitative technique includes several forms of research, including associational, descriptive, and intervention studies. Descriptive research includes the investigation and explanation of the research issue, together with the examination of the characteristics of the study sample and their actions in connection to the problem under study. The study use quantitative methodologies to examine a research issue in the district of Peshawar. Hence, the most suitable approach for collecting data from participants is via the use of questionnaires.

Population and Sample Size

The population of the study was health care employees of "Hospital" in KP Peshawar. The participants were employees of nursing department only. Sampling is a critical process that requires careful selection of a representative sample from the whole population to facilitate subsequent analysis. The researcher extrapolates the findings to the whole population based on the outcomes seen in the sample. Probability and non-probability sampling are two broad categories of sampling methods (Taherdoost, 2016). Probability sampling is a method that relies on the concepts of probability theory to ensure that every sample taken from a population has an equal and fair opportunity to be chosen (Tehseen, Ramayah, & Sajilan, 2017).

The sample size calculated by the following formula $n = N/1 + N*(e)^2$

so the sample size is $n=361$

Data Collection Method

The technique of collecting data is based on written surveys, which are preferred due to their efficiency and suitability for handling sensitive

information (Dillman, 2000; Salant & Dillman, 1994). An individual engaged in research will directly gather primary data via the use of questionnaires, interviews, experiments, and observations (Brewerton & Millward, 2006). The questionnaires were used for primary data gathering. According to Kothari (2004), a questionnaire is the only means of gathering genuine data from many persons situated in various geographical regions, which cannot be achieved by other techniques of data collecting. The surveys were disseminated to the personnel of the hotel sector. The researcher scheduled a meeting with the respondents and asked them to allocate some time to complete a questionnaire.

Analytical Tool with Model Specification

Data was collected on the chosen variables to accomplish the primary objectives of the present study. A standardized questionnaire was used to gather data from participants. The questionnaire was created in accordance with the study requirements. This study used a quantitative research approach. The organized questionnaire was included topics such as corporate social responsibility, perceived organizational support, and training and development. The HR departments of hospital district Peshawar will thoroughly analyze all of these aspects.

Data Analysis

The data analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 21. Various tests were conducted using the SPSS software. The present research used SPSS graphics to perform correlation and mediation analysis, aiming to investigate the impact of employer branding component on employee retention in district Peshawar.

Analysis of the Study

The surveys were initially divided into two sections. The first phase consisted of a demographic component, which included questions about the age groups and experiences of the respondents, as well as determining their gender. Furthermore, a questionnaire was specifically created to investigate the

impact of employee branding on employee retention. A total of 450 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. We got a response from a total of 398 individuals, out of which 37 were rejected due to incomplete failure. Therefore, the final count of cleared responders was 361

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Respondents Age Percentage (N=361)

Age Group	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
18 to 22	3.60%	3.60%	3.60%
23 to 26	52.90%	52.90%	56.50%
27 to 31	31.30%	31.30%	87.80%
32 to 37	6.92%	6.92%	94.72%
38 to 50	5.28%	5.28%	100.00%

The table displays the distribution of individuals across different age groups. It categorizes people into five age brackets: 18 to 22, 23 to 26, 27 to 31, 32 to 37, and 38 to 50. Each row presents the frequency and percentage of individuals falling within that specific age range. For instance, the age group 18 to 22 comprises 3.60% of the total sample, while the 23 to 26 age bracket represents the largest portion with 52.90%. The "Cumulative Percent" column demonstrates the cumulative percentage of individuals accounted for up to that specific age group, reflecting a progression from younger to older demographics. This data enables an understanding of the age distribution within the surveyed population, highlighting the predominant age ranges and their cumulative contribution to the total population sample.

Respondents Gender (N=361)

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	43.49%	43.49%	43.49%
Female	56.51%	56.51%	100%

The table presents the gender distribution in a certain population sample, categorizing people into two groups: males and females. Each row displays the frequency and proportion of persons belonging to a certain gender. The dataset is mostly composed of females, who account for 56.51% of the overall sample, while men comprise 43.49%. The “Cumulative Percent” column displays the total proportion of persons accounted for in each gender group, with the female category reaching 100% since it encompasses the whole sample. This data offers valuable information on the gender distribution of the surveyed population, emphasizing the percentage of men and females and their combined contribution to the entire dataset.

Respondents Tenure (N=361)

Experience Range	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
1 - 3	41.27%	41.27%	41.27%
4 - 6	43.75%	43.75%	85.02%
7 - 9	14.40%	14.40%	99.42%
14 - 16	0.58%	0.58%	100.00%

Table presents a summary of the distribution of tenure among the respondents, based on a sample size of 361 persons. The table classifies participants according to their duration of experience within a certain range. The experience ranges are as follows: 1 to 3 years, 4 to 6 years, 7 to 9 years, and 14 to 16 years. The data in each row displays the frequency and proportion of respondents who belong to a certain tenure range. The tenure range of 4 to 6 years is the most common, representing 43.75% of the overall sample. It is followed by the range of 1 to 3 years, which accounts for 41.27%. The “Cumulative Percent” column displays the total proportion of respondents accounted for within each tenure range. The data adds up to 100% in the last category, reflecting the complete sample. This data provides insights into the distribution of respondents according to their length of service, emphasizing the most common tenure ranges and their combined representation in the

entire respondent group.

Responding question to “The organization has fair attitude toward employee” N=361

Response	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	26.03%	26.03%	26.03%
Agree	38.22%	38.22%	64.25%
Neutral	16.89%	16.89%	81.14%
Disagree	6.09%	6.09%	87.23%
Strongly Disagree	12.77%	12.77%	100.00%

The data in Table displays the answers of 361 individuals in relation to their assessment of the organization’s fairness towards its workers. The replies are classified into five categories: “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” The frequency and percentage of participants who selected each answer choice are shown in each row. Specifically, 26.03% of the participants expressed strong agreement with the organization’s fair treatment of workers, while 38.22% indicated agreement. The “Cumulative Percent” column displays the total percentage of replies received up to each category, illustrating the gradual accumulation of participant responses. The data indicates that a significant majority of respondents, including 64.25% of the total, expressed strong agreement or agreement with the statement. In addition, 16.89% of the respondents expressed a neutral stance, whereas 6.09% opposed, and 12.77% strongly disagreed. This data offers valuable insights into workers’ assessments of the organization’s fairness procedures, revealing both regions of agreement and areas of disagreement among the respondents.

Responding Question to” Employee are Expected to Follow Rule and Regulation” N=361

Response	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	207	57.34%	57.34%
Agree	81	22.43%	79.77%
Neutral	18	4.98%	84.75%
Disagree	8	2.21%	86.96%
Strongly Disagree	47	13.04%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table displays the answers of 361 participants to the question on their expectations regarding workers' compliance with rules and regulations inside the firm. The replies are classified into five categories: "Strongly Agree," "Agree," "Neutral," "Disagree," and "Strongly Disagree." The frequency and percentage of participants who chose each answer choice are shown in each row. For example, a significant majority of respondents, accounting for 57.34%, strongly agreed that workers are obligated to adhere to rules and regulations. Furthermore, a total of 22.43% of respondents expressed agreement with this assumption. The "Cumulative Percent" column demonstrates the gradual accumulation of participant replies, reaching 100% at the conclusion of the table. In addition to the participants' replies, the table also contains a row labeled "Total" which indicates that all 361 participants provided a response to the question. This data offers valuable insights into the predominant views among workers about organizational expectations for adherence to rules and regulations. It specifically highlights the level of agreement or disagreement among the group of respondents.

Responding Question to” Humanitarians Organization gives Back to Society” N=361

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	57	15.78%	15.78%
Agree	115	31.86%	47.64%
Neutral	135	37.40%	85.04%
Disagree	36	9.97%	95.01%
Strongly Disagree	18	4.99%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 participants’ views on humanitarian organizations’ influence on society. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Rows represent the frequency and percentage of respondents who chose an answer. For instance, 15.78% strongly agreed with humanitarian organizations’ contribution to society, whereas 31.86% agreed. The “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses accumulating to 100% at the table’s end. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This dataset provides useful insights on people’s views of humanitarian groups’ societal contributions. The respondents’ views ranged from agreement to disagreement.

Responding question to” The enterprise evaluate my contribution toward welfare” N=361

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	85	23.54%	23.54%
Agree	139	38.50%	62.04%
Neutral	95	26.31%	88.35%
Disagree	15	4.15%	92.50%

Strongly Disagree	27	7.50%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

A question on how their organization evaluates their wellbeing contributions is answered in Table 4.2.4 by 361 participants. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Each row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. In particular, 23.54% strongly agreed with their organization’s view of their welfare contribution, while 38.50% concurred. The “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses gradually adding up to 100% at the end of the table. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This dataset shows how organizations rate individual welfare contributions and the respondents’ degrees of agreement or disagreement.

Responding question to” The organization cares about general satisfaction at work” N=361

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	115	31.85%	31.85%
Agree	140	38.78%	70.63%
Neutral	45	12.46%	83.09%
Disagree	25	6.92%	90.01%
Strongly disagree	36	9.99%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 respondents’ opinions on the company’s work satisfaction efforts. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Each row shows the number and percentage of respondents who picked a response. 31.85% strongly agreed that the company cares about work happiness, while 38.78% agreed. At the table’s end, the “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses increasing

to 100%. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data highlights respondents’ degree of agreement or disagreement on the business’s perceived caring for work happiness.

Responding to question” Help is available from organization when I have a problem”

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	46	12.74%	12.74%
Agree	137	37.95%	50.69%
Neutral	56	15.51%	66.20%
Disagree	96	26.59%	92.79%
Strongly disagree	26	7.21%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 participants’ opinions on the organization’s help when they need it. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. The organization’s support when presented with a problem was highly agreed upon by 12.74% of participants and less so by 37.95%. At the table’s end, the “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses increasing to 100%. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data shows respondents’ levels of agreement or disagreement on the organization’s perceived availability of aid in times of need.

Responding question to “if given me the opportunity take advantage of me’

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	46	12.74%	12.74%
Agree	182	50.41%	63.15%

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neutral	67	18.55%	81.70%
Disagree	45	12.46%	94.16%
Strongly disagree	21	5.84%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 people’s perceptions of being exploited when given the opportunity. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. For instance, 12.74% strongly agreed with feeling exploited if given the opportunity, whereas 50.41% agreed. The “Cumulative Percent” column tracks participant responses as they aggregate to 100% at the table’s end. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This dataset reveals respondents’ subjective assessments of their vulnerability to exploitation when given opportunity, showing various degrees of consensus or dissent.

Response to “The organization care about my option” N=361

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	77	21.32%	21.32%
Agree	135	37.39%	58.71%
Neutral	97	26.86%	85.57%
Disagree	35	9.69%	95.26%
Strongly disagree	17	4.74%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table summarizes 361 participants’ assessments on how much the organization values their viewpoints. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.”

Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. In particular, 21.32% strongly agreed that the organization cared about their opinions, whereas 37.39% agreed. At the table's end, the "Cumulative Percent" column shows participant responses increasing to 100%. According to the table's "Total" item, 361 people answered the question. It shows how individuals see the organization's openness to their ideas. It indicates respondents' agreement and disagreement.

Responding question to "The organization pay really attention on my welfare"

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	96	26.59%	26.59%
Agree	118	32.68%	59.27%
Neutral	85	23.54%	82.81%
Disagree	36	9.97%	92.78%
Strongly disagree	26	7.22%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 people's opinions about the organization's care for them. The responses are categorized as "Strongly Agree," "Agree," "Neutral," "Disagree," and "Strongly Disagree." Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. For instance, 26.59% strongly agreed that the company prioritized their well-being, whereas 32.68% concurred. The "Cumulative Percent" column shows participant responses gradually adding up to 100% at the end of the table. The table's "Total" row shows that all 361 participants answered the question. This information shows how individuals see the company's care for them. Respondents agree or disagree in various degrees.

Responding question to “My organization provides us online training courses”

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	70	19.39%	19.39%
Agree	70	19.39%	38.78%
Neutral	110	30.47%	69.25%
Disagree	77	21.32%	90.57%
Strongly disagree	34	9.43%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 participants’ responses to a question on employer-offered online training course accessibility. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. 19.39% of participants strongly agreed that their firm offered online training courses, while an equal amount agreed. The “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses gradually adding up to 100% at the end of the table. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data shows respondents’ opinions on workplace online training tool accessibility.

Responding question to “my organization organizes various conferences, workshops and training”

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	134	37.11%	37.11%
Agree	94	26.03%	63.14%
Neutral	66	18.28%	81.42%
Disagree	38	10.52%	91.94%
Strongly disagree	29	8.06%	100.00%

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Total	361	100.00%	

Table 4.2.11 shows 361 respondents' opinions on their company's conference, seminar, and training management. The responses are categorized as "Strongly Agree," "Agree," "Neutral," "Disagree," and "Strongly Disagree." Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. In particular, 37.11% of participants strongly agreed that their company organizes varied conferences, seminars, and training sessions, whereas 26.03% agreed. The "Cumulative Percent" column shows participant responses gradually adding up to 100% at the end of the table. The table also contains a "Total" row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data shows people's perceptions of organizations' professional development efforts. It also shows respondents' agreement or disagreement.

Responding question to "Training program comprehensive"

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	167	46.26%	46.26%
Agree	105	29.08%	75.34%
Neutral	34	9.41%	84.75%
Disagree	30	8.31%	93.06%
Strongly disagree	25	6.94%	100.00%
Total	361	10	

Table 4.2.12 shows 361 respondents' replies on the training program's coverage. The responses are categorized as "Strongly Agree," "Agree," "Neutral," "Disagree," and "Strongly Disagree." Each row shows the number and percentage of respondents who picked a response. For example, 46.26% of participants strongly agreed that the training program was complete, whereas 29.08% agreed. At the table's end, the "Cumulative Percent" column shows participant responses increasing to 100%. The table also contains a

“Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data shows respondents’ levels of agreement or disagreement on whether the training program meets their needs.

Responding question to “my organization offers opportunities to work on foreign projects”

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	95	26.31%	26.31%
Agree	50	13.85%	40.16%
Neutral	110	30.47%	70.63%
Disagree	95	26.31%	96.94%
Strongly disagree	11	3.06%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table 4.2.13 shows 361 participants’ responses to a question about foreign project opportunities in their company. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. In particular, 26.31% strongly agreed that their business offered abroad project opportunities, whereas 13.85% only agreed. At the table’s end, the “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses increasing to 100%. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data shows how individuals see overseas project opportunities in their organization. Respondents agree or disagree in various degrees.

Responding to “skill development is continuous process in organization

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	168	46.53%	46.53%
Agree	94	26.03%	72.56%
Neutral	45	12.46%	85.02%
Disagree	31	8.58%	93.60%
Strongly disagree	23	6.40%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 respondents’ views on skill development as a corporate process. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. For instance, 46.53% strongly agreed that business skill development is continual, whereas 26.03% agreed. At the table’s end, the “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses increasing to 100%. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This data reveals how individuals see the organization’s talent development strategy. Respondents agree or disagree in various degrees.

Table 4.2.15: Responding to “my organization invests heavily in training and development of its employee”

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	140	38.78%	38.78%
Agree	68	18.83%	57.61%
Neutral	82	22.71%	80.32%
Disagree	40	11.08%	91.40%
Strongly disagree	31	8.60%	100.00%

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Total	361		

361 participants answered a question on their organization’s staff training and development investment in Table 4.2.15. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Every row shows the frequency and percentage of participants who picked a given response. In particular, 38.78% strongly agreed that their firm invests much in training and development, whereas 18.83% simply agreed. The “Cumulative Percent” column aggregates participant responses to 100% at the end of the table. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This dataset sheds light on employees’ views about their company’s training and development. Respondents agree or disagree in various degrees.

Responding to “my organization communicates clear advancement path for its employees”

Groups	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	73	20.22%	20.22%
Agree	136	37.67%	57.89%
Neutral	85	23.54%	81.43%
Disagree	40	11.08%	92.51%
Strongly disagree	27	7.49%	100.00%
Total	361	100.00%	

Table shows 361 respondents’ opinions on whether their company communicates career growth to employees. The responses are categorized as “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Each row shows the number and percentage of respondents who picked a response. 20.22 percent of participants strongly agreed that their firm effectively communicated a clear career path for workers, while 37.67 percent

agreed. The “Cumulative Percent” column shows participant responses gradually adding up to 100% at the end of the table. The table also contains a “Total” row, indicating that all 361 participants answered. This statistic shows respondents’ opinions on their firm’s growth prospects.

Descriptive Statistic

In this study on the "Effect of Employer Branding Dimensions on Employee Retention: Evidence from the Health Sector in District Peshawar," descriptive statistics provide an initial overview of the data collected through the structured questionnaire. The sample consists of healthcare employees from various organizations within the district, ensuring a diverse representation of the population. Descriptive statistics summarize key characteristics of the data, including measures of central tendency (mean, median) and dispersion (standard deviation, range).

T-test of respondents of the study N=361

T-Test	Group 1 (Male)	Group 2 (Female)	Independent Variables	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	t-value	p-value
Employee retention	157	204	Corporate social responsibility, Perceived organizational support, Training & development	36.65	33.15	1.256	0.002

The findings of a t-test performed on the research respondents are shown in Table No. 4.3.1. The overall sample size for the study was N=361. The t-test is used to compare the mean scores of two groups, Group 1 (Male) and Group 2 (Female), on the independent variables of corporate social responsibility,

perceived organization support, employer branding dimension, and training & development. This comparison is made in relation to the dependent variable of employee retention. The table presents the average disparity between the two groups, the measure of variability, the t-value, and the associated p-value. The mean difference suggests that, on average, girls outperformed men by 36.65 points on the independent variables. The standard deviation quantifies the dispersion of scores within each category. The t-value of 1.256 indicates that the difference in means is 1.256 standard deviations apart from the predicted mean difference due to random chance. The p-value of 0.002 shows a statistically significant difference in means, demonstrating a substantial disparity in scores between men and females on the independent variables in connection to employee retention.

Regression Analysis of Variables

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	Adjusted			
		R-squared	R-squared	F-value	p-value
Employee retention	Corporate social responsibility, organization support, Employer Branding Dimension, Training & development	0.632	0.625	56.78	0.001

A regression study on employee retention and several independent factors is provided in Table 4.3.2. Independent variables explored include CSR, perceived organization support, employer branding, and training & development. The table displays R-squared, modified R-squared, F-value, and p-value. R-squared displays how much independent factors explain dependent variable variation. An R-squared score of 0.632 implies that independent variables explain 63.2% of employee retention variation. Model predictors

lower the adjusted R-squared to 0.625. The regression model is significant with an F-value of 56.78 and p-value of 0.001. Employee retention is affected by corporate social responsibility, perceived organization support, employer branding, and training & development.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant role of employer branding dimensions in enhancing employee retention. The findings suggest that factors such as organizational culture, compensation and benefits, career development opportunities, and work-life balance strongly influence employees' decisions to stay with an organization. A well-established employer brand not only attracts top talent but also fosters employee commitment, reducing turnover rates. Moreover, the study underscores the importance of aligning employer branding strategies with employees' expectations and job satisfaction levels. Organizations that invest in building a positive employer brand through effective leadership, transparent communication, and supportive work environments tend to experience higher retention rates. In conclusion, employer branding serves as a strategic tool for talent management, contributing to long-term organizational success. Future research can explore industry-specific employer branding strategies and their varying impacts on employee retention across different sectors. Organizations should continuously evaluate and enhance their branding efforts to maintain a competitive edge in attracting and retaining skilled employees. For further exploration the variables such as compensation, work flexibility and job satisfaction can be used. Reward systems, HR capacity and career planning initiatives are also important. Employee branding, work value and collaboration can play a role. These elements can act as moderators and mediators. This study did not examine moderation. Future research can be including a moderator variable. It can examine how CSR initiatives and talent management influence employee retention and performance.

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